

Mustaqeem Ahmed – Law Of Extra Force

Original Definition of Extra Force:

When a Newton Force (engine force or applied force) acts on an object and an additional force acts simultaneously causing a change in acceleration, this additional change in acceleration is called Extra Force.

Here:

Newton / Engine Force = Main force

Extra Force = Force that increases or decreases acceleration

Velocity is referenced to Newton force; Extra Force does not directly define velocity, but shows its combined effect through micro-level changes in acceleration.

Car + Air Example:

Same Direction Air: Car moves forward while air moves in the same direction. Air gives the car an extra push, producing positive acceleration. This works as Extra Force; it is interaction force, not free energy.

Opposite Direction Air:

Car moves forward while air comes from the front. This reduces - acceleration and acts as negative Extra Force.

Additional Internal Force Example (Compression door / Window):

When a compressible structure, such as a spring-loaded compression door or window system, is pushed and then returns to its original position, an additional internal force of extra is generated whenever an external Newtonian force is applied.

This internal force contributes to the overall

system dynamics and assists the object in moving forward without producing free energy.

The internal compression mechanism acts as an extra internal force that combines with the external Newtonian force, resulting in motion that is noticeably greater than that produced by the external Newtonian force alone.

Note: Internal forces present within a mechanical system are useful and contribute to motion enhancement, internal ,not energy creation.

Important Rule:

Extra Force is always equal to or less than Newton Force, never more.

It is purely mechanical and does not violate any law.

Magnet Repulsion – Extra Force (FE) – Accelerating Body / Car Example:

If a same-pole magnet is placed at the back of an accelerating object, it repels and provides supporting Extra Force.

Engine force = Newton Force

Magnet push = Extra Force

Combined effect = better acceleration

Magnet is not an energy source, only a medium for force interaction, distribution, and direction management. **In this -> Electro Magnet, spring**

Newton Third Law – Spread Loss Mechanisms Set-Up (Toy Car Experiment):

Normally, action = reaction. But by attaching two same-pole magnets, spring, or electromagnet at the back of the object, repulsion creates spread and distribution effects.

Mechanism A . Mechanism A & B – Combined Force-Path Control Using Magnetic Repulsion only .

In this setup, a magnet attached at the back side of the body generates forward acceleration (+) through magnetic repulsion. Along with this forward repulsion, an opposite reaction / backward impact is also produced, which normally would oppose acceleration. **In this setup Electro Magnet system, spring]**

Mechanism A: [Used Electro magnet system]

In this case, the opposite reaction magnet is fixed using a metal structure to the lower body part of the system, such as the back wheel support or lower chassis. Because of this fixing, the backward repulsion does not act directly opposite to motion. Instead, the force is shifted into the lower body, where it gets spread and distributed inside the structure. Through this distribution, a useful vertical net component is created in the lower body. A major portion of the opposing force converts into support and spread loss, rather than direct backward opposition. After this force-path handling, the repulsion force from the second magnet attached to the body remains effective in the forward direction, resulting in net acceleration equal to Newton / engine force plus Extra Force combined.

Mechanism B:

In the same setup, instead of fixing the opposite reaction to the lower body, the opposite reaction magnet is fixed through a metal length from the back side to the top body or front

frame. Due to this length, the backward reaction does not remain a direct backward force. While traveling through the metal length, the force converts into torque and spread loss, and a major portion of the opposite reaction shifts into loss through torque. Because of this, the backward opposing effect becomes weak. Meanwhile, the magnet attached to the body continues to produce repulsion in the forward acceleration (+) direction, so Extra Force remains effective and combines with Newton / engine force, improving net acceleration.

A In both mechanisms, there is no free energy. The improvement comes purely from force-path control, spread /distribution, and torque-based loss management, which allows the forward Extra Force to remain effective when combined with Newton Force

B In both mechanisms, the opposite reaction is smartly handled through structural fixing and force-path control, so it does not act as a direct backward opposing force but gets converted into spread, distribution, and torque-based loss while the forward Extra Force remains effective.

Noted ----> Here,

Is In this setup Centerized electro magnet repulsion !!

Not only magnet!

opposite reaction impact is not completely eliminated; a partial impact always remains. Because of this remaining impact and continuous loss factors, no free energy is produced, velocity is not micro-changeable at will, and the system remains bound to real-world mechanical limits but a part of the force becomes useful through redirection and distribution, but total energy remains conserved and no free energy is generated.

Velocity-Based Physics:

Velocity is taken as the primary reference because the system is non-ideal and loss forces are always present.

Extra Force does not change independently.

Newton / Engine force is not perfectly constant and continues to change at the micro level.

These micro-level force and acceleration variations appear externally as surface velocity changes, even though surface acceleration is not directly observable.

Internal Extra Force effects are not clearly noticeable in real-world conditions due to continuous losses; therefore, Extra Force is not fully changeable.

Motion is provided only when micro-level acceleration change occurs—this is the actual

cause of motion.

U-Shape Structured Force - Straight Line /

When force acts at the center point of a body, it does not travel straight, but spreads inside the body.

U-Shape role: distributes force width-wise, reducing center spread loss.

Force applied from the center is most effective; off-center force produces torque and loss.

Torque - Deep Physics:

Torque is not a separate force, it is the rotational effect of spread force.

Surface torque is visible, but deep-level spread force decides how much torque is useful vs lost due to direction change.

Equation Explain :

Newton Force = FN

Extra Force = FE

$FE = M \times \Delta a$

Total Force = TF = FN + FE

Example:

Mass = 5 kg

Acceleration change: $2 \rightarrow 4 \text{ m/s}^2 \rightarrow \Delta a = 2$

$FE = 5 \times 2 = 10$

Rest State Extra Force - Logical Principle:

At rest, Newton force is not applied, so motion does not occur.

Extra Force exists logically, but motion is only caused by Newton/Engine force because it is Changeable .

Half-body Distribution Example:

Rest / Half-Body Equation:

FE / Combined Acceleration = FE / Newton (A.C) = 10 / 4 = 2.5 (Extra Force contribution)

Distribution: 2.5 + 2.5 + 2.5 + 2.5 = 10

Newton Force FN = 2.5 (half-body) × Combined acceleration 4 m/s²

Extra Force FE = 2.5 (half-body)

Velocity reference = 4 m/s²

Combined Force = 20

Summary Equation:

FE + FN = M × Δa

At rest, acceleration impact per half-body → Force Extra / Combined Acceleration = Force Extra, Newton Force

value = 10 / 4 = 2.5, 2.5,,

ΔFE 10 / 4 ms C.A = [half kg 5 - 2.5] × C.A

[kg half 5 - 2.5 newton] × 4 ms C.A = Total Force → (10 , 10){ FN ,FE]

Fixed force

Extra Force ≤ Newton Force

Note: Motion / acceleration is observable only after Newton force is applied.

No free energy—only logical combined force effect.

Fuel Efficiency – Core Purpose:

Reduced spread loss

Improved motion

Better velocity response

Less fuel for same work

Applications: Cars, trains, aircraft, rockets, fluid ships

Law Statement:

Extra Force can be created via any mechanism or engineering design (internal + external).

Extra Force exists and is useful in accelerating bodies and rotational phenomena.

In real-world, Newton force spreads at the center and weakens.

By controlling spread through structure, width distribution, internal mechanisms, and interaction forces, effective Newton force increases.

Extra Force is not independent energy, but combined with Newton force, it improves velocity response and fuel efficiency.